

Governance Transformation in the Pharmaceutical and Medical Device Sectors After the 2020–2024 Policy Reforms: A Strategic Management Theory Approach

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to analyze the strategic transformation in the governance of the Secretariat of the Directorate General of Pharmaceuticals and Medical Devices (Setditjen Farmalkes) after the revision of the Ministry of Health's 2020-2024 Strategic Plan (Renstra). Using a qualitative approach and documentary case study, data was collected from three main documents: RAK Revision 4, Wasalkes 2024 Performance Report, and 2023 Audited Financial Report. Analysis was conducted based on the Strategic Management Theory framework, which includes the process of strategy formulation, implementation, and evaluation. The results showed that the reformulation of strategic indicators, such as changes in the target values of Bureaucratic Reform and Budget Performance, reflected the institution's adaptation efforts to the demands of institutional reform. The implementation of the strategy is quite effective, as reflected in the high budget realization and the achievement of technical indicators, such as CPAKB and the supervision of class C and D medical equipment. However, the decline in budget performance scores in 2024 indicates the challenge of maintaining accountability in the final phase of the strategy. Intensive cross-sector coordination and utilization of information systems such as Seralkes and the supervision dashboard strengthen the effectiveness of digital-based governance. This study recommends strengthening the data-based monitoring and evaluation system and developing a more integrated information system across units.

I. INTRODUCTION

The transformation of public governance over time has increasingly adopted the Strategic Management Theory approach, which originally emerged in business management, but is now proving relevant for public sector organizations. Nurkholis et al, emphasize the important role of strategy, systematic implementation, and outcome-based monitoring in improving the effectiveness of public administration (Nurkholis et al., 2023) . A similar study conducted by Arvina et.al, in a hospital showed that adaptive strategic management improves operational efficiency and service quality, with technology utilization and innovation integration as key success factors (Arviana et al., 2025) . In the context of Indonesia's health services, the Directorate General of Pharmaceuticals and Medical Devices (DG Pharmaceuticals) has an important role in ensuring the quality and distribution of health products. The revision of the Ministry of Health's Strategic Plan 2020-2024, marks substantial changes in strategic performance indicators:

emphasizing accountability, budget efficiency, as well as the use of digital technology and cross-unit coordination (Ministry of Health RI, 20) .24

Harahap & Wardhono's research on health centers in Indonesia revealed that strategy documents are often not integrated with actual implementation, even though the Balanced Scorecard (BSC) is used as a monitoring tool. Jakarta Puskesmas uses BSC as a performance evaluation tool but encounters gaps between strategic plans and operational practices (Harahap & Wardhono, 2020) . Another study conducted by Schnell et al, emphasized that the main challenges in public sector performance management are low data quality, limited managerial capacity, and lack of outcome-based evaluation, which causes strategic planning documents to often be symbolic (Schnell et al., 2021) . The digital era brings new paradigms such as Digital- Era Governance (DEG) and Whole-of-Government (WoG). Pande et al. (2025) emphasize that the success of digital governance in government is highly

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dependent on a coordinated Whole-of-Government approach, especially in addressing the challenges of digital divide, digital literacy, and cross-sector leadership (Pande et al., 2025).

Adrian et al. showed that the implementation of the Executive Information System (EIS) in Jakarta enables near real-time reporting of COVID-19 data, accelerates epidemiological analysis, and supports data-driven decision making by policy makers (Adrian et al., 2021). Meanwhile, Juliansyah et al. emphasized that the implementation of Electronic Medical Records (EMR) in Indonesian health facilities improves service efficiency, accelerates access to patient data, and strengthens clinical decision making quickly and accurately (Juliansyah et al., 2024). Research by Tenggono et al. (2024) investigated the role of digital readiness and dynamic managerial capabilities in driving strategic renewal in private hospitals in Indonesia. They found that institutional pressure supports digital readiness, while managerial competencies accelerate digital strategy implementation (Tenggono et al., 2024). From a theoretical perspective, Learning Health Systems (LHS) provides a framework for health systems that integrate data, research and clinical practice in a sustainable manner. This concept is relevant because the revised Strategic Plan should be elevated to the operational level through a data-driven feedback loop.

This research aims to fill the gap in public strategic management studies in the Indonesian health sector. The focus is on the transformation of governance at the Secretariat of the Directorate General of Pharmaceuticals after the revision of the Strategic Plan, through the lens of Strategic Management Theory: starting from strategy formulation, implementation mechanisms, digitization of processes, to cross-unit synergies. Some of the main questions raised are: How is strategic management implemented after the revision of the Strategic Plan? How does digital readiness and managerial capacity support transformation? How does stakeholder engagement occur within the Directorate General of Pharmaceuticals? The contribution of this research is twofold. Academically, it expands the application of Strategic Management Theory in the public health sector in developing countries. Practically, the results offer recommendations on strategy design, capacity building, and data utilization in monitoring unit performance.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Strategic Management Theory in the Public Sector

Ritonga (2020) explains that the strategic management process includes strategy formulation, implementation, and evaluation, which in the public sector must be adapted to the bureaucratic structure and the dynamics of interests between stakeholders (Ritonga, Z. 2020). Ongaro and Ferlie developed the concept of public entrepreneurs as strategic

actors in public organizations, who operate within political constraints, limited tenure, and bureaucratic pressures, so public strategy cannot be equated with the private sector approach (Ongaro & Ferlie, 2020).

The KNKG states that good public sector governance should create long-term public value through transparency, collaboration and accountability across sectors (General Guidelines for Indonesian Public Sector Governance, 2022). This concept then encourages public organizations to not only be oriented towards outputs, but also outcomes and public value. In this case, the changes in the Ministry of Health's Strategic Plan mark a significant shift in institutional strategy and demand in-depth managerial understanding.

Governance Transformation in Public Health Institutions

Strategic transformation in public health systems generally includes institutional reform, budget efficiency, and strengthening the role of technology in governance. The study by Giovanni et al emphasizes that the success of hospital strategy depends heavily on the integration between strategic planning, management information systems, and an organizational culture that is adaptive to change (Giovanni et al., 2024). In the context of the Ministry of Health, the revision of the 2020-2024 Strategic Plan through PMK No. 13 of 2022 is a response to the needs of national health system reform. One of the key changes is the adjustment of performance indicators and the strengthening of data-based accountability systems. This requires support from units such as the Secretariat of the Directorate General of Pharmaceuticals, which acts as a strategic and administrative coordinator (Kemenkes RI, 2024).

Relevance of Digital Era Governance and Whole-of-Government

Irfan emphasized that digital integration in the public sector requires transformation in service systems, organizational structures, and work culture, in order to improve accountability and efficiency of public service governance (Irfan, 2024). The development of the *Executive Information System* (EIS) by the DKI Jakarta Health Office during the COVID-19 pandemic enables near real-time data reporting through dashboards, thereby accelerating epidemiological analysis and data-based decision-making by policy makers (Adrian et al., 2021).

The OECD emphasizes that a *Whole-of-Government* approach is needed to bring together the expertise and resources of different government institutions to achieve common development goals in an effective and coordinated manner (OECD, 2022). The Whole-of-Government (WoG) approach is also highly relevant, as it requires synchronization across directorates and programs in planning and implementing public strategies. In the context of DGHS, WoG is important to unify efforts between

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medical device control, pharmaceutical supply, and institutional reform.

Previous Research: Gap and Learning

Several studies have revealed challenges in strategy implementation in public health institutions. Harahap and Wardhono and Harahap showed that although the Balanced Scorecard was implemented in health centers, the integration between strategy and operational implementation was still weak (Wardhono & Harahap, 2020). Giovanni et al, highlighted that the weakness of strategy implementation in the public sector is often caused by a lack of monitoring and weak managerial capacity, which causes planning documents such as the Strategic Plan to not run optimally (Giovanni et al., 2024).

Tenggono et al, added that the success of the transformation strategy is strongly influenced by digital readiness and dynamic managerial capabilities (Tenggono et al., 2024). This means that the revised strategy as stated in the Ministry of Health Strategic Plan will only be effective if it is supported by digital readiness, HR training, and adaptive leadership.

III. METHODOLOGY

Research Type and Approach

This research uses a descriptive qualitative approach with a documentary case study design. The aim is to describe and analyze the transformation of governance strategies at the Secretariat of the Directorate General of Pharmaceuticals and Medical Devices (Setditjen Farmalkes) after the revision of the Ministry of Health's Strategic Plan (Renstra) 2020-2024. This approach was used because the research wanted to understand the context, substance of change, and policy implementation process from relevant official documents.

Nurahma and Hendriani cite Yin (2018) that case studies are very appropriate for exploring contemporary phenomena in real-life contexts, especially when the boundaries between phenomena and context are not clear and researchers do not have direct control over the events under study (Nurahma et al., 2021).

Data Source

This research fully utilized secondary data, which was obtained through a review of official documents and government publications, among others:

- Activity Action Plan of the Directorate General of Pharmaceuticals 2020-2024 4th Revision,
- Performance Report of Directorate of Medical Devices Supervision Year 2024,
- Financial Report of the Directorate General of Pharmaceuticals for Fiscal Year 2023 (Audited),
- Ministry of Health Regulation No. 13 of 2022 on Amendments to Ministry of Health Regulation No. 21 of

2020 (Ministry of Health Strategic Plan 2020-2024),

- Other supporting documents related to performance, accountability, strategic indicators, and supervision of pharmaceutical and medical device programs.

These sources were used to assess policy changes, indicator achievements, and the dynamics of the organization's strategy in the last five years.

Table 1: Research Variables

No	Variables	Operational Definition	Analysis Indicator
1	Strategy Formulation	The process of adjusting policy directions and strategic performance indicators in planning documents (Renstra & RAK)	Changes in performance indicators
			Output target adjustment
			Adjustment of task structure
2	Strategy Implementation	Implementation of strategic policies in the implementation of organizational programs/activities	Realization of programs & activities
			Budget absorption
			Distribution of technical activities
3	Strategy Evaluation	Measurement of achievements against strategic targets set post-revision	Percentage of indicator achievement (CPAKB, CDAKB, C&D medical devices)
			Output & outcome realization
			SAKIP evaluation score
4	Performance Accountability	Level of accountability for program implementation and use of resources	SAKIP score (2019-2023)
			Budget vs output realization
			Efficient use of funds
5	Governance Effectiveness	Effectiveness of organizational	Number of cross-sector

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		role implementation in supporting the Strategic Plan	activities
			Stakeholder engagement
			Inter-unit coordination
6	Information Technology Utilization	Integration of information systems and digitization of work processes in program management	CPAKB/CDAK B certification information system
			Medical device monitoring dashboard
			Community complaint system

budgeting performance scores (RAK setfarmalkes rev.4, 2024).

Vandersmissen and George state that strategic planning in public organizations must begin with a systematic analysis of the internal and external environment, so that the strategies formulated are able to answer the complexity of the context and create sustainable public value (Vandersmissen & George, 2024).

The establishment of these new indicators also reflects an understanding of the need for indicators that are more challenging and have a strategic impact on outcomes, not just output-based indicators such as PAK. In this context, DGHS has taken an adaptive approach to changes in performance indicators as part of the reformulation of institutional strategy. This is also in line with the findings of Ongaro & Ferlie who assert that emphasize that public sector organizations need to adjust their *strategic intent* to external dynamics, including the expectations of regulatory authorities and stakeholders, so that the strategies formed remain relevant and publicly accountable (Ongaro & Ferlie, 2020).

Furthermore, the revision of indicators shows a response to the performance value-based accountability system that increasingly requires organizations to work more integrated and impactful. Based on previous performance evaluation results that have achieved the "AA" category, this indicator adjustment not only confirms past successes, but also shows readiness to face new targets that are more complex and systemic.

Thus, the formulation of the postrevision strategy of the Strategic Plan is not only administrative, but an effort to reallocate the strategic focus of the institution to maximize accountability and governance. Haug et al, state that digital transformation in the public sector is not only technical, but also demands institutional *learning* and *whole-of-government* coordination to produce transformative and sustainable change, which strengthens the position of the Directorate General of Pharmaceuticals as a strategic actor in Indonesia's health sector reform (Haug et al., 2024).

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Strategy Formulation Variable

Table 2: Changes In Strategic Indicators Of The Directorate General Of Pharmaceuticals

Year	Previous Indicator	Revised Indicator (PMK No. 13/2022)	Target
2020-2021	Percentage of Pharmacist/Assistant Pharmacist PAK completion	-	90-92%
2022	Bureaucratic Reform Score	Bureaucratic Reform Score	35,5
2023	Bureaucratic Reform Score	Bureaucratic Reform Score	35,7
2024	-	Bureaucratic Reform Score	90,01
2022-2024	-	Budgeting Performance Score	89-91

Changes in strategic indicators in the revised Renstra 2020-2024 document reflect a shift in the organization's strategic focus from administrative operational aspects to governance and outcome-based institutional performance dimensions. One significant change is the replacement of the indicator "completion of Credit Score Assessment (PAK)" with "budgeting performance score", and the setting of an ambitious target for Bureaucratic Reform (RB) in 2024 of 90.01, up dramatically from 35.7 in 2023. The shift in indicators indicates a *strategic reframing* to deal with structural reform demands from the Ministry of PAN-RB, as well as an adjustment to the Ministry of Finance's SMART application-based measurement method in evaluating

Strategy Implementation Variable

Table 3: Program Realization and Budget Absorption of Setditjen Pharmalkes

Main Activities	Budget Ceiling (Rp)	Realization (Rp)	Uptake Percent age
Pharmaceutical Production & Distribution	433.219.000	365.773.800	84,43%
Supervision	200.000.000	194.660.000	97,33%

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n of Medical Device & PKRT			
Total Farmalkes Program	22.474.000.000.000	22.181.000.000.000	98,70%

The implementation of the post-revision strategic plan shows excellent performance in terms of budget absorption and program implementation. The high level of realization, especially in the medical device supervision program which reached more than 97%, reflects the effectiveness in the implementation of activities based on previously prepared plans. Kornelius et al, found that alignment between strategic plans and actual resource distribution acts as an important link between strategic planning and organizational performance, in line with the interactive approach ala Miles et al. (2014) (Kornelius et al., 2020).

This achievement also indicates that the Directorate General of Pharmaceuticals has implemented the principle of *strategic alignment*, namely the suitability of the formulated strategy with technical policies and program implementation activities. The high level of implementation in budget utilization, particularly for pharmaceutical production and distribution activities, indicates that basic service functions remain a priority amidst the revision of the medium-term strategy.

However, it should be noted that high absorption does not always reflect strategic effectiveness if it is not accompanied by measurable outcome achievements. Therefore, it is important to conduct an integrative evaluation between expenditure achievements and program performance achievements. This is supported by research by Kurniadi that the performance reporting and monitoring information system developed with the *Balanced Scorecard* approach and the *Scrum* method is able to increase organizational responsiveness to operational dynamics, thus supporting the successful implementation of strategies in an adaptive and measurable manner (Kurniadi et al., 2023).

Strategy Evaluation Variable

Table 4: Achievement of Technical Performance Indicators of Ditwasalkes

Indicator	Target	Realization	Percentage of Achievement
CPAKB Certification	90%	93,72%	104,13%
Supervision of Medical Devices C & D	90%	92,50%	102,80%

The results of the strategy evaluation show that the majority of technical performance indicators have reached and even exceeded the target. CPAKB certification as an instrument of quality assurance for medical device production, was achieved up to 104% of the set target. This shows the effectiveness of Ditwasalkes' role in expanding supervision and encouraging business compliance, in line with the concept of performance-focused strategy (Tenggono et al., 2024).

This achievement also indicates the successful utilization of information systems for the certification process, as well as strengthening the risk-based regulatory function. Afshar and Shah emphasize that the application of the Balanced Scorecard framework in public sector organizations enables comprehensive strategic evaluation through four main perspectives-financial, customer, internal processes, and learning and growth-thus supporting outcome-based decision making and strengthening strategic feedback mechanisms (Afshar, 2025).

However, the unavailability of explicit CDAKB achievement data is a weakness in reporting consistency. This shows the importance of strengthening the overall performance information management system so that all strategic indicators can be measured and analyzed systematically. Evaluation of strategies needs to be done not only based on numerical achievements, but also the process and constraints of implementation.

Performance Accountability Variable

Table 5. Achievement of Budgeting Performance Value

Year	Target	Realization	Percentage
2022	89	89	100%
2023	90	90	100%
2024	91	80,1	88,02%

The decline in the budgeting performance score in 2024 to 80.1 from a target of 91 signals a decline in the effectiveness of budget management. While historically previous years have consistently achieved 100% of the target, this downward trend indicates challenges in consistency of budget control, performance reporting, or possible constraints on program implementation efficiency. Carreno emphasized that implementing a *continuous feedback loop* allows organizations to adapt in real-time to changes through the use of dynamic employee feedback. This approach creates an ongoing evaluative process to inform strategy adjustments and improve organizational resilience (Carreno, 2024) . Performance accountability is not only reflected in financial statements, but also in the ability of institutions to maintain consistent performance standards over the long term.

In addition, this decline can also be interpreted as the impact of the pressure of new indicators set in the revised

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Strategic Plan which are more complex, demanding adaptation in terms of human resources, reporting systems, and K/L reward mechanisms. Cinar et al, emphasize that the national context and internal capacity of public organizations greatly influence the type of innovation that emerges. They point out that external pressures such as economic crises, transparency demands, or political reforms will only result in effective innovations if they are supported by administrative readiness, technological resources, and internal institutional structures. This is in line with Ferede's (2024) idea that public evaluations should consider the balance between reform pressures and internal readiness (Cinar et al., 2024).

Governance Effectiveness Variable

Table 6: Number of Strategic Coordination Meetings

Meeting Type	Total
Cross program & sector	43
Regulation socialization	10+
Strengthening lab network	5

The high intensity of coordination across programs and sectors indicates the strong commitment of the Directorate General of Pharmaceuticals to implement a *whole-of-government* approach in operational strategies. A total of 43 coordinative meetings were reported in 2024, involving cross-sector actors and supporting the synchronization of regulations and the networking of medical device testing laboratory services. The OECD emphasizes that the effectiveness of cross-ministerial development governance relies heavily on strong coordination, clear division of mandates, and joint accountability mechanisms. This is in line with the view of Dunleavy et al. (2006) that governance effectiveness is not only measured by the end result, but also by the collaborative process between actors that strengthens the systemic capacity of institutions through integration and digitization (OECD, 2022).

Such intensive coordination strengthens *governance capacity*, which is the ability of institutions to bring together different functions and strategic partners to achieve common goals. This is an important foundation in supporting the sustainability of institutional reforms. The OECD emphasizes that the effectiveness of cross-ministerial cooperation depends on strong coordination, clear division of roles, and joint accountability mechanisms. This is in line with Ciancarini et al who point out that the intensity of meetings between stakeholders reflects the dynamics of regulatory changes that demand technical adaptation and collaborative communication on an ongoing basis (OECD, 2022).

Information Technology Utilization Variable

Table 7: Strategic Information Systems Used by Wasalkes

System	Main Functions
Seralkes	CPAKB and CPPKRTB Certification
Surveillance Dashboard	Monitoring of Class C & D Medical Equipment
SIPT (Health OSS)	Integration of business licenses and supervision

The utilization of information technology within Ditwasalkes is one of the main pillars in supporting effective and efficient strategy implementation. The Seralkes application, SIPT, and supervision dashboard have been used as a medium to manage the certification, licensing, and risk-based supervision processes in a more systematic and transparent manner. This shows a real integration between technology and institutional strategy. Dunleavy's *digital-era governance* concept is very relevant in this context, because technology is used not only as an administrative tool, but also as a driver of policy transformation and public services, this is in line with the OECD which shows that the effectiveness of cross-ministerial cooperation in global development depends heavily on the use of technology to strengthen overall institutional coordination, transparency and accountability (OECD, 2022).

Monitoring dashboards, for example, have facilitated quick decision-making based on field data evidence. On the other hand, challenges remain in data interoperability across systems and the continued maintenance of digital systems. The use of this technology also supports the principle of *evidence-based management*, which emphasizes the importance of data in strategy formulation and adjustment. Therefore, a reliable, integrated and sustainably used information system is an absolute requirement for the successful implementation of long-term strategies in the public health sector (Tenggono et al., 2024).

V. CONCLUSION

This study shows that the strategic transformation of governance within the Secretariat of the Directorate General of Pharmaceuticals and Health after the revision of the 2020-2024 Strategic Plan reflects a fairly consistent application of strategic management principles, especially in the aspects of strategy formulation and program implementation. The shift in strategic indicators from administrative to more substantive indicators such as the value of bureaucratic reform and budgeting performance shows the institution's efforts to adjust to the demands of institutional reform and increased public accountability. This indicator revision represents *strategic reframing* in strategic management theory, where organizations respond

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to performance evaluations and national policy changes by adapting their strategic objectives more progressively.

Strategy implementation has been relatively effective, as evidenced by the high level of budget absorption and activity realization. Supervision and certification activities, such as CPAKB and class C and D medical equipment, are not only implemented according to the target, but even exceed the planned achievements. This strengthens the argument that the successful implementation of the strategy is strongly influenced by system readiness and synchronization between implementing units. Nonetheless, challenges arise in the aspects of performance evaluation and accountability, especially with the declining achievement of budgeting performance scores in 2024, which indicates room for improvement in efficiency and strategic reporting. Evaluation is important not only as the final stage of the strategy, but as a reflection of institutional success in dealing with complex changes.

Organizational governance has also demonstrated effectiveness through the high intensity of cross-sector coordination meetings, supporting a *whole-of-government* approach in the implementation of priority programs. Strong coordinative processes have strengthened policy synergies between Ditwasalkes and other technical partners. On the other hand, the utilization of information technology such as the Seralkes system and supervisory dashboard has become the backbone of the digitalization of supervision and certification that supports evidence-based and real-time decision-making. This is consistent with *digital-era governance* principles that prioritize efficiency, transparency, and integration between units in public sector management.

As a suggestion, the results of this study recommend the need to strengthen the data-based evaluation system for all performance indicators, including the integration of CDAKB data which is still not systematically recorded. It is also necessary to optimize the use of information systems that are more interoperable between directorates and implementing units, so that the strategy monitoring process can be carried out cross-functionally and continuously. To maintain the consistency of strategy achievements in the long term, institutions need to build managerial capacity and internal monitoring systems that are not only responsive to national indicators, but also adaptive to technical and operational challenges at the field level. A collaborative approach and continuous organizational learning will be the key to success in maintaining the sustainability of the transformation of DG Pharmalkes' governance strategy in the future.

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